

Big Five Personality Traits and Training Transfer: Evidence from Banking Sector in Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 12, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: August 26, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Personality Traits, Training Transfer, Training, Human Capital Development</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5277897</p>	<p><i>Training transfer is mainly aimed to increase the capacities, abilities and work performances of employees. It has seen that major objective of training is to apply the knowledge and prepare the staffs for improving their performances. Literature showed that there are many factors that can play significant role for effecting training transfer in the organizations and personality traits have seen as important predictors. Current study was aimed to evaluate the role of Big Five personality traits towards training transfer. The study was based on quantitative techniques where data was collected through survey based questionnaire. After conducting the survey for targeted population, collected data was recorded in SPSS for statistical analysis. Results of statistics showed that personality traits i.e. Agreeableness, Extraversion, Openness, Neuroticism and Conscientiousness have found significant association with training transfer. This study presented that personality traits can play important role for increasing the transfer of training that furthermore prove very beneficial for the working organizations where employee can put the gained knowledge into practice to increase their practical performances. This study also recommends the future directions for incoming researchers.</i></p>

Introduction

Human capital is the backbone of any organization. In order to enhance the capacity of the human capital and to achieve the required skills, knowledge and attitudes; organizations spend hefty budgets on training and development activities (Lacerenza et al., 2017). Current era of fierce competition in the marketplace compelled organizations to have a highly skilled workforce to get a handsome share in the market (Noe, Hollenbeck, Gerhart & Wright, 2019; Bhatti & Kaur, 2010). Moreover, organizations invest in training and development activities; because the world is a global village now and need of standardized international training certifications is need of the hour for multinational workforce (Nwokeiwu, Ziska, Achilike, 2019). Organizations spend heavy budgets on trainings on yearly basis, but somehow unfortunately trainings fall short to deliver the expected output (Ford & Prasad, 2018). So, it is essential for them to evaluate that whether the budgets spent on training and development activities justify themselves or not. It was recorded in 2014, the organizations in US alone spent over \$70 billion every year (Schaefer, 2015) and average training cost per employee was calculated recently \$986 per year (LorriFreifeld, 2018). Another recent report on training industry by LorriFreifeld (2019) calculated that organizations in US alone spent over \$83 billion every year while in Pakistan expenditure on training and development activities is yet not documented.

Training and development is one of the major functions of HRM that come into action when there is a need to improve or instill the knowledge, skills and abilities into the employees of the organization to have a competitive edge over competitors (Burt 1992; Hansen, 2002). The level of capacity built and range of knowledge and skills acquired by an organization can be the reason of its success or failure. Trainings are an important component of almost every organization; as it improves the performance and productivity of not only the workforce but also the organization as a whole (Bhatti & Kaur, 2010). So, if training and development activities improve the productivity of the workforce; the question arises that how much quantifiable impact they have and moreover does that impact justifies the dollars spent on that activities (Bartel, 2000; Burke & Hutchins, 2007).

To, answers the above asked question and evaluate the effectiveness of the training program, organizations typically develop certain parameter and mechanisms through which they can evaluate the effectiveness of the training in terms of training transfer. Normally in the training literature, terms like; Learning transfer, knowledge transfer, training transfer or transfer of training are used to indicate that how much knowledge is being gained by a trainee and how much is transferred at the real job setting (Baldwin & Ford, 1988). Trainings can basically be described as a very organized effort initiated by the organization with a view to enhance the knowledge, skills, and abilities of its workforce (Garavan, 1997) and once the trainings are complete; organizations then assess the transfer of training (Goldstein & Ford, 2007). In this assessment of

transfer of training, the organizations basically assess how much the training has actually proved to be successful (Kasim & Ali, 2011) like to what extent the trainee can apply the newly learned knowledge, skills, and abilities to their work (Baldwin, Ford & Blume, 2009; Baldwin et al., 1988) because at the end of the day it is the transfer of training that ensures the better employee performance and service level that will ultimately affect organizational performance (Zumrah, 2015).

Big Five Personality Traits:

Personality traits have been recognized as a set of distinctive characteristics that an individual owns and these traits keep significant influence on motivation, cognition and individual behaviors (Ryckman, 2012). In order to explain the element of "Big Five", a personality trait theory, there made an initial move presented by McDougall (1932). The "Big Five" theory has referred the five important dimensions that had presented by scholars like Eysenck and Eysenck (1985) and Cattell and Kline (1977). These five important traits are Extroversion, agreeableness, neuroticism, openness and conscientiousness. This research model offers the extended support to understand the differences in personalities, groups of diverse nature and individual characteristics for evaluating the personality differences among individuals concerning with different fields and cultures. These personality traits have been evaluated across instruments and being observed by different researches (Cortina, et al., 1992). In the following sections, there are discussion about these important personality dimensions and how these dimensions associate with training transferability.

Training Transfer:

The basic assumption of learning transfer, training transfer of simply knowledge transferability is referred as the individual's performance to improve through an effective training procedures (Burke & Hutchins 2007). Baldwin and Ford (1988) has explained the training transfer as a degree of trainee's application of knowledge, attitudes and skills being achieved through job related training. Broad and Newstrom (1992) have defined the training transfer as a regular application of staffs to their job and transferability of knowledge and associated skills achieved through training to the cross areas of jobs. Noe and Schmitt (1986) have explained that it is the well designed and planned experience for bringing a consistent change among employee's attitudes, skills and knowledge.

Noe and Schmitt's (1986) explanation is specified for training, the basic concept of transferability has been applied to the training program. Staffs receive the knowledge aimed in a training schedule and its transferability is mainly associate for increasing the capacities, abilities and work performances of employees (Stewart, et al. 2008). It has seen that major objective of training is to apply the knowledge and prepare the staffs for improving their performances.

The study of Chiaburu and Marinova 2008 has highlighted that pre-training factors of motivation are major components and keep significant impact of individual performances. Performance changes has been supposed as an important factors that training transferability caused and establish the strong basis for fulfilling the true meaning of training transfer. The attitudes, skills and knowledge attained during training are referred as performance improvements for the individuals in the context of job related activities and tasks (McSherry & Taylor 1994). In this study, transfer of training has been viewed as the arrangement of obtaining knowledge and learning. It has also found that effective transferability is primarily focused by the ability of employees for practicing the associated knowledge to improve the performance of their jobs.

The results of study conducted by Chiaburu and Marinova have also highlighted the role of supervisor's support for managing good transfer of training in a healthy environment. Baldwin and Ford's (1988) have argued that learning and its application, it has resulted that there must be generalized results of learning that can be prove supportive in daily jobs for a longer period of time. The findings of Yamnil and McLean (2001) have reflected the basic concept of learning application by emphasizing on effective transfer and a change in performance in a positive way. In another study, it has evaluated that factors that prove as the barrier forces in the way of effective transferability of training in the organizations where employees get training and get back to their workplaces. It has found that in the absence of transferability of training there are negligible results of such trainings (Gaudine & Saks 2004).

The results showed that cost of organizational training may not be prove as cost effective unless there will be performance increase among trainees that can tribute towards the organizational performance. Hence, it has highlighted from the different studies that performance improvement is the major areas that proves as a main indicator for training effectiveness (Velada et al., 2007). In the context of organizational objectives, knowledge application being demonstrated to the trainees must be observed by organizations to highlight the complexities if training transfers.

Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses:

Below mentioned figure explains the conceptual research model for this research. Apart from the fact that few motivational theories not offer importance for personal as an important indicator of required transfer of training, however, these theories significantly associate with the process of relating personality traits with the transfer of training. On the basis of such facts, present study upholds the theoretical foundations on the basis of two important theories i.e. expectancy theory and personality trait model. Above introduction well explains the

contextual association of these two theories however, in following discussion, there augmentations to explain the relevance of these selected theories with the objectives of this research.

As explained above, there is major fact of conscientiousness is performance orientation that persuades the trainee for improving his or her Performance of job through knowledge and learning. In consistence with the indications of expectancy theory, there are key elements i.e. expectancy, instrumentality and valence that supports the employee performance and motivation (Yamhill and McLean, 2001). It has directed that higher level of achievement orientation of employee results the improved work performances (valence), it is also evident that increased performance of employees is significantly associated with their level of learning (expectancy), it is also indicated that increased learning efforts definitely leads towards improvements in working performances (instrumentality) (LePine, et al., 2000).

In connection with achievement orientation, it is referred as the capacity of trainee to set his specified objectives that particularly attract the action, attention and effort. Consequently, a trained owns the super motivation for performing will and poses goal related actions (Locke and Latham, 2006) that furthermore leads towards improved working performances.

Naquin and Holton (2002) has resulted the insignificant relationship between extraversion and transfer of training, there were positive effects and it was indicated that extraversion needs to be retained in effective transferability of training.

It has stated that in trainings, extraverted trainees keep high ambitions, optimism and confidence in learning activities (Yamkovenko and Holton, 2010). These trainees own the tendencies of setting higher level of training goals and believes to attain the objectives through extra efforts in trainings. It has found that motivation level of trainee's increases as the working performance through learning increases (Yamkovenko and Holton, 2010). On the other hand, the aspect of being sociable for an extraverted trainee is found as a critical factor that play significant role for creating the levels of motivation and contributes to apply the learning thoughts on jobs.

A highly agreeable individual proved to be supportive in such traits when gone through the training process is more probable to develop the individual dedication and improved performance that further contribute toward the organization productivity through higher influences of training transfer. It has found that agreeableness is significantly important that other personality traits to predict the transferability of training through MTIWL because this personality trait keeps the aspects of helpfulness (Barrick et al., 2002) that proves critical in learning activities and transfer along with complete dedication and cooperation.

Conscientiousness and Training Transfer:

Conscientiousness has been categorized as trait reflects the behavior of individuals like organized, dutiful, completing assignment on time and able to complete the allocated task in correct way. Conscientiousness keeps three main characteristics i.e. dependability (Careful and responsible), achievement orientation (persistent and hardworking) and orderliness (organized).

Hence, Furthermore, it has found that task Conscientiousness has been referred as the person's degree of self-control and need for persuading the objectives, persistence and carefulness. Conscientiousness is significantly related with transfer of training. Huang and Bramble (2016) have presented the findings that Conscientiousness is such a trait that associates with training and regulatory process and results of training. Conscientiousness importantly influences the transfer of training in such situation where tasks are dynamic and very difficult.

Huang et al. (2016) have conducted conscientiousness is not an effective predictor and meta-analysis and explained the results that conscientiousness is not an effective predictor of maximum transfers of training (i.e. trainee's degree of transfer towards job), although, it is the traditional transfer (an extent where trainee is willing to transfer).

Different researches like Blume et al. (2010); Yamkovenko and Holton (2010) and Herold et al. (2002) have found that learning ability in the training or specific capacity for applying the on job training keeps significant and positive association with conscientiousness. This research is aimed to evaluate the influence of conscientiousness towards transfer of training, hence current study hypothesizes the following:

H1: There exists significant relationship between conscientiousness and transfer of training.

Extraversion and Training Transfer:

Extraversion has been defined as the socialized, high spirited and energetic. These individuals own the capability to function with increased efficiency and effectiveness for expanding their network to get the information that are essential for attaining the goals of trainings. Extraversion persons are energetic, ambitious, outgoing and assertive that usually present the interaction abilities, properties of activeness, being dominant, bold and status seekers (Mount et al., 2005).

As per explanation of According to Costa and McCrae (1991), Barrick et al. (2005), Hogan (1986), and McCrae and Costa (1987) extraversion people could be categorized as an assertive, ambitious, cheerful, sensation-seeking, active and sociable. There exists the strong evidences that significant association lies between training, transfer, motivational and extraversion. There are very little researches that revealed the relationship among stated variables (Barrick et al., 2002).

Those participants in training who were highly sociable has seen with exhibiting high level of performance though training relative to different types of occupations. In order to understand the deeper concepts of extroversion that how it related with the environment of training, Naquin and Holton (2002) have suggested that extroversion significantly affects the motivation level of trainees for improving their working performances by effective learning though a social process. Assisting the significant influence of sociability on the training transfer Lemke, Leicht, and Miller (1974) have indicated the results of undergraduates that training in heterogeneous persons or groups offers better working performances for training transferability.

It has suggested by the scholars that low ability trainees were less likely to adopt the strategy solution on their personal behalf, hence, an extrovert in training play significant role for verbalization of effective strategies and prove so supportive for making good training transfers. Likewise, Olivera and Strauss (2004) have presented the results though puzzle solving offered high degree on individual transferability to learning through knowledge and cognition shared procedures. In contrast to shared learning, along a persona has not presented the same results. Furthermore studies in organizational staffs for the role of extroversion and transfer of training associated this warranted.

H2: There exists significant association between extraversion and training transferability.

Agreeableness and Training Transfer:

Agreeableness indicates the dimensions of personality of being helpful, altruistic and sympathetic (Major et al., 2006). Agreeableness also keeps the characteristics like tolerant, courteous, good-natured, flexible, trusting, forgiving, co-operative and soft-hearted (Judge et al., 2007). Previous researches have presented the pessimistic view keeping the significant impact of agreeableness on the transfer of training (Blume et al., 2010). The summarized results are that agreeableness may not assist the transferability arrangements that are loaded by stress and regular change (Yamkovenko and Holton, 2010). Hence, any participants in training who scores higher in agreeableness can meet the situation of high demand (Yamkovenko and Holton, 2010) because of lack of orientation in achievement.

Rowold (2007) has presented that those trainees who were agree to assist others and make efforts for positive interactions in social context also put their energies for attentive learning and hence they also apply the learned knowledge into practice for increasing their job performances.

In accordance with the findings of Lievens et al.'s (2003), there is a significant association between staffs motivation and agreeableness to learn through trainings in different sessions. In another research, Naquin and Holton (2002) stated that those trainees who found to be helpful in supporting their organizations usually achieve success and usually showed more inclined behavior for acting as committed.

It is evident from the findings of different scholars that helpfulness and supportive quality of trainees is the main key of agreeableness (Barrick and Mount, 1991). In accordance with the expectancy theory, any trainee own high scores in his agreeableness show the significant tendency for accepting the application of training in practical sense and it proves very beneficial for trainee as well as for the organization to improve work performances in effective way. The major trait of employee to be helpful is usually reinforced by the impact of training transfer, hence present study hypothesizes the following:

H3: There exists significant association between agreeableness and training transfers.

Openness to Experience and Training Transfer:

Openness to experience defined as the degree of making adjustments in connection with newer ideas or required situations, it usually tends to be fit into the new opinions with increased degree of tolerance and agreeing towards a newer concept.

Openness to experience has been well characterized by the people who own sensitive, creative and flexible. It is the trait that usually represent the wish for personal growth (Mount et al., 2005). Results of meta-analysis showed that openness to experience is significantly associated with the learning activities (Barrick & Mount, 1991).

The result of openness to experience have found as limited across different jobs, as Barrick and Mount(1991) showed the results of a study that high level of training proficiency related with openness to experience. In another study Herold et al. (2002) has stated that openness to experience supports the trainees to capitalize better in initial training successes and to obtain required skills in faster way. This type of intellectual curiosity supports the trainees for exploring the flexibility in learning and adopting the newer skills. On the basis of these results, present research has hypothesized that:

H4: There exists significant association between Openness to Experience and training transfers.

Neuroticism and Training Transfer:

Neuroticism has been defined as a negative aspect of instability and it usually associates with the uncertain environment. Neuroticism is an inability of a person to arrange the stability of emotional and psychological aspects. Neuroticism keeps the specific characteristics that includes lower confidence, anxiety and propensities for experiencing the emotions of nativity. As this propensity keep negativity in emotions, any person related to neuroticism scores very high must own less chances of positive responses and attitudes

towards the transfer of training. Hence, it has resulted that such type of individual re negatively associated with training transferability. The important characteristics like stability of emotions and anxiety results minimized performance in training and furthermore its transferability. Those persons who own neuroticism trait are more like to experience the different types of problems like low performance, unhappiness, disturbed relationship with colleagues and uncompleted tasks etc. These all problems prove as a barrier in the way of employee motivation and mobility for acquiring the knowledge, abilities and skills during training, hence current researchhypothesizes the following:

H5: There exists significant negative association between Neuroticism and training transfers.

Big Five Personality Traits

Figure. 1
Conceptual Model

Methodology

Design

This study has based on cross sectional design where data has collected in quantitative way at a single time. This research is positive in which study hypotheses have judged on the basis of statistical analysis.

Participant and procedure

A list consisting on trainees who have attended the training of management program was collected form Malaysian public sector organization. After the time of three months of training completion, participants have sent e-mails to respond against the research survey. Those e-mails were containing the online survey in the form of self-rated questionnaire. This survey data was collected after three months of training completion on the future basis to acquire appropriate opportunities for employing the trainingthoughts into practice (Burke and Hutchins, 2007; Pham et al., 2013). IN this process of data collection, there were strict ethical considerations followed.

These survey participants were working employees in different public sector companies in Malaysia. These employees have attended the different training programs being organized by the public sector training provider organization in Malaysia.

From the survey of 440 employees, there was usable data of 131 trainees with the rate of response of 29.8%. There were 67.9% participation of women and 32.1% of men in this research survey. In this collected response

of survey, 51.1% of respondents were related to age group of 30-39 years and 38.2% of participants were owning the Malaysian education certificate. Lastly, nearly half of the respondents 43.5% were working in different organization for last 6-10 years.

Measures

This research has employed the five-point Likert scale, self-rating questionnaire for obtaining the data from targeted participants. This self-rated scale was criticized due to the impact of common method variances (CMV) by different researchers like Podsakoff et al. (2003). Additionally, it has found that there are no strong evidences that suggest inability to measure trainee's performance in correct way (Chiaburu and Tekleab, 2005). Actual evidences proposed that convergence among self-rating and measuring objectives for transfer of training (Chiaburu et al., 2010).

This self-rating survey questionnaire was consisted on close ended items were translated in Urdu and English and this scale was adopted from the instrument of existing study. Back-translation has been employed for translating the survey questionnaire from English into Urdu with the help of experienced translator of both languages. A tutor of human resource management and other two practitioners of organizational trainings have extensively reviewed the self-rating survey questionnaire for ensuring the association of this self-rating with local parameters. This self-rating research instrument has included the demographic information for evaluating the personal characteristics like age, education, and gender and seniority level.

Personality traits

The items for measuring personality traits have adopted from Big Five Inventory (John et al., 1991). Conscientiousness has measured by four items and there is sample i.e. "I see myself as a person who perseveres until the task is finished." Extraversion has been measured by five items for example "I see myself as someone who generates a lot of enthusiasm." Thirdly, Agreeableness has been measured by four items and example is "I see myself as a person who is supportive to others."

Training transfer

The construct for training transfer has measured by ten items and this scale has been adapted from Fecteau et al. (1995) and Xiao (1996). One of the sampled item was "The harder I learn during the training course, the better I perform my job."

Results

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) has been conducted for exploring the data in SPSS-26 followed by (CFA) confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modeling (SEM) by AMOS-24. Lastly, there was processed a series of comparison of two models for testing the moderation impact of e-social influence towards other variables in study.

In order to evaluate the impact of exogenous variables towards endogenous variables, an approach based on two steps by Anderson & Gerbing (1988) had implemented. Though CFA, it has evaluation of validators for convergent and discriminant. Convergent validity had tested for ensuring the measurement of items that were associated with each other in the same construct and discriminant validity checked the confirmation of measures that were not related with each other in constructs (Hair et al., 1998). In an SEM analysis, there was an assessment of goodness of fit, χ^2 value, normed fit index (NFI), non-normed fit index (NNFI or TLI), comparative fit index (CFI), and the root mean squared error of approximation (RMSEA) (Hair et al., 2010). Lastly, there were proceedings for structural path to judge the research hypotheses (Hair et al., 2010).

Exploratory Factor Analysis of Big five personality traits and training transfer:

Exploratory factor analysis through method of principal components and varimax rotation has processed for the questions of personality because it has been recommended method for measurement of personality items (Tsao & Chang, 2010). The resulted value of Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) that evaluates the sampling adequacy was (0.977) and the resulted significance value of Bartlett's test of Sphericity is (.000) that significantly indicated that the underlying items were more appropriate to run the factor analysis. In exploratory factor analysis, it has identified the six dimensions for personality traits (5 dimensions), training transfer (one dimension).

There were a series of factors where seven measuring items have been deleted that also includes three important items i.e. openness to experience, two items from conscientiousness and one each from training transfer and extraversion. In reliability analysis, results showed that personality traits and training transfer has resulted the values of Cronbach alpha above than .07 that significant verified the internal consistency of scales. The explanation of six factors is 56.8% of total variance (Table 1).

Table 1

EFA Analysis reliability and

Items	Factor Loading					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
TT1						.645
TT2						.645
TT3						.638

TT4						.663
TT5						.698
ExtraVer1		.735				
ExtraVer2		.731				
ExtraVer3		.766				
ExtraVer4		.760				
ExtraVer5		.777				
ExtraVer6		.694				
ExtraVer7		.719				
Agreeable1	.718					
Agreeable2	.745					
Agreeable3	.762					
Agreeable4	.763					
Agreeable5	.737					
Agreeable6	.705					
Agreeable7	.694					
Agreeable8	.667					
Agreeable9	.745					
Con1					.653	
Con2					.658	
Con3					.711	
Con4					.713	
Con5					.677	
Con6					.697	
Con7					.695	
Neu1			.649			
Neu2			.722			
Neu3			.740			
Neu4			.716			
Neu5			.728			
Neu6			.610			
Neu7			.666			
Neu8			.688			
Open1		.744				
Open2		.759				
Open3		.766				
Open4		.711				
Open5		.754				
Open6		.771				
Open7		.742				
Eigenvalue	4.24	3.34	2.07	1.46	1.44	1.20
% of Variance	41.74	59.53	64.35	67.75	71.11	73.91
Cronbach's Alpha	.949	.961	.941	.935	.923	.929

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

a. Rotation converged in 8 iterations.

Common method bias (CMB)

This research has collected the cross sectional data by means of a single instrument, hence common method bias (CMB), could be presented against the responses (Podsakoff et al., 2012). In order to check the important threats of CMB, an approach of multipronged has been employed in current research. Firstly, the survey instrument was designed in such way that can significantly able to reduce the CMB at respondents-level.

In this regard, reverse items have used for securing the attention of participants to respond the survey. Secondly, there processed a test of Harman's single-factor for assessing the conceptual variables in research model. This process has not revealed any CMB problem as a single factor and cold be explained as 41.74% with respect to total variance that is significantly less than the maximum limit of 50% (Podsakoff et al., 2012).

Table 2
Harman's single-factor test

Factor	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.249	41.743	41.743	22.249	41.743	41.743
2	3.348	7.787	59.530			
3	2.074	4.823	64.353			
4	1.462	3.399	67.752			
5	1.447	3.366	71.118			
6	1.204	2.799	73.917			

Measurement model

In this research, measurement model was evaluated through a test of reliability and consistency for the constructs. Table 4 showed the factors loading, average variance and combined reliability. It has seen that all values of factor loading were in the range of 0.66–0.89, hence it has exceeded the threshold limit of 60% (Carmines & Zeller, 1979). The average values between 59% and 70%, seen higher than the cut-off 50% (Fornell&Larcker, 1981). The resulted values of CR have ranged from 0.81 to 0.95, were also higher than the standardized threshold of 0.7. Hence, it has found that the processed model owns good convergent validity. Further, determining the discriminant validity, it has evaluated pair wise relationship and square root of AVE (Fornell&Larcker, 1981) suggested value.

There was high correlation among variables valued 0.57 by <0.71 (Podsakoff&MacKenzie, 2012). Additionally, square roots of AVE has seen as greater than associated relationships. Table 5 has presented the relationship of off-diagonal values with the square root of AVE in diagonal position. Lastly, heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) has also implemented for evaluating the discriminant validity through latest recommendations (Henseler et al., 2015).

It has seen that HTMT resulted values were significant lower than value of threshold 0.85, hence, discriminant validity has reaffirmed (Table 6). Furthermore, it has also confirmed the goodness of fit for this research model by chi-square (χ^2), percentage of variance 41.74%.

Table 3
Reliabilities and Factor loadings

No.	Constructs	CR	AVE	Loadings Range
1	Agreeableness	0.950	0.677	.778-.860
2	Extraversion	0.961	0.777	.837-.914
3	Openness	0.941	0.696	.789-.883
4	Neuroticism	0.938	0.657	.776-.891
5	Contentiousness	0.924	0.634	.774-.823
6	Training Transfer	0.930	0.727	.830-.871

Above table has well explained the result of reliability and factor loading values. It has seen that reliability values for each variable has resulted the value above than .070 showing the acceptable level of internal consistency for each scale in the model. On the other hand, factor loading range for each factors in model showed the results in the range of .774 as minimum and .914 as maximum that has indicated the acceptance of items being employed in the research instrument and proved its validity.

Table 4
Correlation and square root of AVE

	Agreeableness	Extraversion	Openness	Neuroticism	Contentiousness	Training Transfer
Agreeableness	0.823					
Extraversion	0.655***	0.882				
Openness	0.583***	0.664***	0.834			
Neuroticism	-0.612***	-0.781***	-0.711***	0.810		
Contentiousness	0.794***	0.653***	0.603***	-0.624***	0.796	

Training Transfer	0.753***	0.717***	0.691***	-0.709***	0.754***	0.853
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Above table of correlation results showed that there exists significant relationship among research variables. As agreeableness has resulted relationship with extraversion valued .65, with openness 0.58, with neuroticism - 0.61, with contentiousness 0.79, with contentiousness 0.76 and dependent variables training transfer valued 0.75. This relationship of agreeableness with other independent and dependent variables showed that there is significant relationship with all variables. Neuroticism has shown the significant but negative relationship with all variables.

Table 5
Results of hypothesis testing

	Hypotheses and paths	Estimates	S.E	CR	Sig.	Results
H1	TT <--- Agreeableness	.264	.060	4.439	***	Supported
H2	TT <--- Extraversion	.140	.064	2.435	.015	Supported
H3	TT <--- Openness	.188	.060	3.782	***	Supported
H4	TT <--- Neuroticism	-.152	.069	-2.558	.011	Supported
H5	TT <--- Contentiousness	.245	.063	3.995	***	Supported

Discussions of the Results:

Although there are lot of researches to evaluate the factors associated with training transfers, the results of previous researches supported the arguments that there exists different factors that significant effect the training transfer. Current study has also presented the role of big five personality traits towards training transfer. Hence, this study highlighted the potential opportunities for practitioners and academicians to employ these results to different contexts.

Results of this study has showed that all five personality traits i.e. Agreeableness, Extraversion, Openness, Neuroticism and Contentiousness keep significant relationship with each other as well as with training transfer. This relationship of Big Five Personality traits with training transfer is consistent with the results of previous studies which also indicated the association of personality traits with transferability of trainings in a positive way.

In results of direct relationship of all five personality traits i.e. Agreeableness, Extraversion, Openness, Neuroticism and Contentiousness have found with acceptable significant level i.e. ($p < 0.05$). The resulted variances of each independent variable towards dependent variable is positive except Neuroticism. These results have revealed that importance of big five personality traits that can influence the transferability in significant way. These results for these dimensions of personality are consistent with respect to prior studies for associating with trainingtransfers.

Results of this study are in lined with the findings of Huang and Bramble (2016) who have presented that conscientiousness as the person's degree of self-control and need for persuading the objectives, persistence and carefulness. Conscientiousness is significantly related with transfer of training. Hence, conscientiousness is such a trait that associates with training and regulatory process and results of training.

The results of this study for signifying the role of extraversion trait to influencetraining transfer showed that low ability trainees were less likely to adopt the strategy solution on their personal behalf, hence, an extrovert in training play significant role for verbalization of effective strategies and prove so supportive for making good training transfers. These results confirms the findings of Olivera and Strauss (2004) that presented the results though puzzle solving offered high degree on individual transferability to learning through knowledge and cognition shared procedures.

Findings of this research for agreeableness indicated the significant impact of agreeableness on the transfer of training. These results are supported by Blume et al. (2010). Hence, any participants in training who scores higher in agreeableness can meet the situation of high demand due to the lack of orientation in achievement.

It has revealed from the statistical results of this study that that high level of training proficiency related with openness to experience. Prior studies like Herold et al. (2002) has also confirmed that openness to experience supports the trainees to capitalize better in initial training successes and to obtain required skills in faster way. This type of intellectual curiosity supports the trainees for exploring the flexibility in learning and adopting the newer skills.

The results of this study for neuroticism and training transfer showed negative and significant. This propensity keep negativity in emotions, any person related to neuroticism scores very high must own less chances of positive responses and attitudes towards the transfer of training. Hence, it has resulted that such type of individual re negatively associated with training transferability. The important characteristics like stability of emotions and anxiety results minimized performance in training and furthermore its transferability.

Managerial Implications:

In addition to theoretical aspects, present research offers very important insight for SMEs' owners/managers and general practitioners to implement the findings. Findings of previous researches prove significant support in the favor of personality traits that play significant role to effect the transfer of training. However, present research contributes to develop clear understanding of managers, owners and other supervisors in the organizations to integrate and develop strategic approach for training results and focus on effective transferability. The result of this study also offered support for policy makers to craft effective policies and increase their understandings about personality traits for enhanced training transfers. Results of this study indicated the way forward for managers and owners in the organizations to offer support though shared ideas for accommodating the different traits towards learning environment and that make trainees able for learning well and employ learnt knowledge to increase organizational performance.

Theoretical Implications:

Present research work is mainly based on prior research for evaluating the role of personality traits towards training transfer. In present study, it has found that there is significant role of five personality training to affect the transferability of organizational trainings. Previous studies have focused different aspects of training for evaluating its transfer, these factors are training environment, trainee's capability or training equipment. Apart from the fact that those factors also play significant role for influencing transfer of training, this research has focused on Big Five Personality traits and came up with results that these personality traits keep significant relationship with transfer of training. On the basis of such facts, present study upholds the theoretical foundations on the basis of two important theories i.e. expectancy theory and personality trait model.

In accordance with expectancy theory, there are key elements i.e. expectancy, instrumentality and valence that supports the employee performance and motivation (Yamhill and McLean, 2001). It has directed that higher level of achievement orientation of employee results the improved work performances (valence), it is also evident that increased performance of employees is significantly associated with their level of learning (expectancy), it is also indicated that increased learning efforts definitely leads towards improvements in working performances. The results of this study have added to the body of existing knowledge and linked the training transfer with personality traits. These results for personality traits have also found consistent with previous research works, it could prove very supportive for organizations to understand and craft effective strategies to manage the good transfer of trainings.

Limitations and Future Research Avenues:

Present research keeps few imitations that can offer a strong basis for incoming researches. The important limitation of this research is that it has collected the data in single time and one source, hence the results of this study may not be generalized for complete sector. The authors of this study have encouraged the incoming researches for including public and private organizations to have deep insight and clear understanding of personality traits towards training transfer. In future researches, this study recommends the comparative analysis of public and private organizations. Additionally, there was collected response though close ended questions, future studies are also recommended to include other ways of data collection that offer the opinion of participants in qualitative way for building efficient understandings about the topic.

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